

EFFECT OF COMPUTER ASSISTED FITNESS TRAINING ON SELECTED CO-ORDINATIVE ABILITIES AMONG COLLEGE WOMEN TARGETBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was designed to examine the effect of computer assisted fitness training on Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability among college women target ball players. For the study, thirty college women target ball players from colleges in and around Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India were selected as subjects. They were divided into two equal groups. Each group consisted of fifteen subjects. Group I underwent computer assisted fitness training for three days per week for twelve weeks. Group II acted as control who did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical education programme. The following variables, namely Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables, namely Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability by using Numbered Medicine Ball Run Test suggested by Peter Hirtz and Backward Medicine Ball Throw Test suggested by Peter Hirtz at prior to and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to analyze the significant difference if any among the groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the ‘F’ ratio obtained by the analysis of covariance, which was considered appropriate. The results of the study showed that there was a significant difference between computer assisted fitness training group and control group on Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability. And, it was found that there was a significant improvement on selected criterion variables such as Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability due to computer assisted fitness training.

Key Words: Computer Assisted Fitness Training, Orientation Ability, Differentiation Ability, College Women Target Ball Players

Introduction:

Computer-assisted fitness training, also known as technology-enabled fitness or digital fitness, refers to the use of computer technology, software applications, and digital devices to enhance and optimize exercise routines, monitor progress, and provide personalized training experiences. This modern approach to fitness integrates technology into various aspects of exercise and training to help individuals achieve their fitness goals more effectively and efficiently. The proliferation of wearable fitness trackers, such as smart watches and fitness bands, has revolutionized how individuals monitor their physical activity, track steps, measure heart rate, monitor sleep patterns, and even analyze workouts in real-time. There has been a surge in the development of fitness apps and online platforms that offer a wide range of features, including workout planning, exercise demonstrations, progress tracking, nutrition guidance, and community support. These apps often leverage algorithms and user data to provide personalized recommendations and adaptive training programs. Many fitness facilities now offer smart gym equipment equipped with sensors, screens, and connectivity features that allow users to track performance metrics, adjust resistance levels, receive instructional guidance, and compete with others in virtual challenges and leader boards.

Computer-assisted fitness training enables personalized workout routines, tailored to individual fitness levels, preferences, and goals. Algorithms analyze user data and feedback to adjust training plans and provide targeted recommendations for optimal results. By collecting and analyzing data on exercise performance, biometrics, and lifestyle habits, computer-assisted fitness platforms can provide valuable insights into progress, trends, strengths, and areas for improvement. Users can make informed decisions and adjustments to their training strategies based on this information. Digital fitness solutions offer flexibility and accessibility, allowing users to access training programs, instructional videos, and fitness communities anytime, anywhere, using smart phones, tablets, or computers. This convenience eliminates barriers to participation and enables consistent adherence to fitness routines. Gamification elements, social features, challenges, rewards, and interactive feedback mechanisms incorporated into computer-assisted fitness platforms help motivate users, enhance engagement, and foster a sense of accountability and camaraderie within the fitness community. Through live streaming, video conferencing, messaging, and coaching features, users can receive remote guidance, support, and encouragement from certified fitness professionals, trainers, and peers, regardless of geographical location. Computer-assisted fitness training represents a modern and innovative approach to fitness and wellness,

leveraging technology to empower individuals, optimize performance, and foster a culture of health and vitality in today's digital age.

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was designed to examine the effect of computer assisted fitness training on Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability among college women target ball players. For the study, thirty college women target ball players from colleges in and around Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India were selected as subjects. They were divided into two equal groups. Each group consisted of fifteen subjects. Group I underwent computer assisted fitness training for three days per week for twelve weeks. Group II acted as control who did not undergo any special training programme apart from their regular physical education programme. The following variables, namely Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability were selected as criterion variables. All the subjects of two groups were tested on selected dependent variables, namely Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability by using Numbered Medicine Ball Run Test suggested by Peter Hirtz and Backward Medicine Ball Throw Test suggested by Peter Hirtz at prior to and immediately after the training programme. The analysis of covariance was used to analyze the significant difference if any among the groups. The .05 level of confidence was fixed as the level of significance to test the 'F' ratio obtained by the analysis of covariance, which was considered appropriate.

Analysis of the Data:

Orientation Ability:

The analysis of covariance on Orientation Ability of the pre and post test scores of computer assisted fitness training group and control group have been analyzed and presented in Table I.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance of the Data on Orientation Ability of Pre and Post Tests Scores of Computer Assisted Fitness Training and Control Groups

Test	Computer Assisted Fitness Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained 'F' Ratio
Pre Test							
Mean	11.01	11.06	Between	0.025	1	0.025	0.17
S.D.	0.36	0.31	Within	4.153	28	0.148	
Post Test							
Mean	9.30	10.90	Between	19.248	1	19.248	23.95*
S.D.	0.38	0.34	Within	22.501	28	0.804	
Adjusted Post Test							
Mean	9.31	10.89	Between	18.741	1	18.741	174.12*
			Within	2.906	27	0.108	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 2 and 28 and 2 and 27 are 3.34 and 3.35 respectively).

Table 1 shows that the adjusted post-test means of computer assisted fitness training group and control group are 9.31 and 10.89 respectively. The obtained "F" ratio of 174.12 for adjusted post-test means is more than the table value of 3.35 for df 1 and 27 required for significance at .05 level of confidence on Orientation Ability. The results of the study indicated that there was a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of computer assisted fitness training group and control group on Orientation Ability.

Differentiation Ability:

The analysis of covariance on Differentiation Ability of the pre and post test scores of computer assisted fitness training group and control group have been analyzed and presented in table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance of the Data on Differentiation Ability of Pre and Post Tests Scores of Computer Assisted Fitness Training and Control Groups

Test	Computer Assisted Fitness Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	Obtained 'F' Ratio
Pre Test							
Mean	10.84	10.97	Between	0.1203	1	0.1203	0.57
S.D.	0.48	0.50	Within	5.8693	28	0.2096	
Post Test							
Mean	8.87	10.91	Between	31.2120	1	31.2120	23.21*
S.D.	0.40	0.42	Within	37.6547	28	1.3448	
Adjusted Post Test							
Mean	8.87	10.90	Between	30.4083	1	30.4083	127.69*
			Within	6.4299	27	0.2381	

* Significant at .05 level of confidence.

(The table values required for significance at .05 level of confidence for 2 and 28 and 2 and 27 are 3.34 and 3.35 respectively).

Table 2 shows that the adjusted post-test means of computer assisted fitness training group and control group are 8.87 and 10.90 respectively. The obtained “F” ratio of 127.69 for adjusted post-test means is more than the table value of 3.35 for df 1 and 27 required for significance at .05 level of confidence on Differentiation Ability. The results of the study indicated that there was a significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of computer assisted fitness training group and control group on Differentiation Ability.

Conclusions:

- There was a significant difference between computer assisted fitness training group and control group on Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability.
- And also it was found that there was a significant improvement on selected criterion variables such as Orientation Ability and Differentiation Ability due to computer assisted fitness training.

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